

TRANSVERSE SHEAR PROPERTIES OF CFRP LAMINATES UNDER STATIC AND IMPACT LOADING

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ABSTRACT

In order to make clear transverse shear properties of CFRP laminates under static and impact loading, unidirectional, angle-ply and quasi isotropic CFRP laminates are tested by the short beam method and a newly-devised electro optical extensometer. This paper presents the first experiment for obtaining the static and impact transverse shear moduli and both transverse failure strains. The experimental values of static and impact shear moduli are fairly in accordance with the analytical ones and the transverse shear moduli of laminates having any fiber orientation angles and any stacking sequences can be calculated by the transverse shear moduli of 0° and 90° . Furthermore, it is shown that the impact transverse shear modulus is larger than the static one and the transverse shear failure strains can be obtained under the static and impact loading.

INTRODUCTION

For the wider use of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) in the field of light weight structures, the static and impact transverse (through the thickness direction) shear properties of CFRP should be made clear. However, while transverse shear strengths have been reported, the transverse shear moduli and failure strains have not because the measurement of these values is difficult in experiments.

This paper presents the first experiment for obtaining the static and impact transverse shear moduli and both transverse failure strains. In order to obtain these values, the difference of vertical

displacement of two points on the neutral axis of the short beam specimen is measured and is divided by the distance of two points. For measuring this difference, an electro optical extensometer is newly devised.

When the fiber orientation angle of unidirectional CFRP is changed from 0° to 90° , the variations of transverse shear moduli and failure strains are measured under the static and impact loading. Furthermore, the transverse shear moduli and failure strains of cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates are also measured under the static loading. These experimental moduli are compared with the analytical ones based on the classical lamination theory and the experimental results of failure strains is discussed using by a three dimensional FEM.

EXPERIMENT

12 kinds of specimens having the laminations of $[0^\circ]_{24}$, $[15^\circ]_{24}$, $[30^\circ]_{24}$, $[40^\circ]_{24}$, $[45^\circ]_{24}$, $[50^\circ]_{24}$, $[55^\circ]_{24}$, $[60^\circ]_{24}$, $[75^\circ]_{24}$, $[90^\circ]_{24}$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{66}$ and $[0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ]_{36}$ are all 3mm thickness. The length of specimen and the distance of the supports are 21mm and 15mm (= 7 and 5 times of thickness) [1], respectively. The specimen has 10mm width and is shown in Fig.1.

Fig.1 Dimension of specimen (Unit:mm)

Since the newly devised electro optical extensometer used here is able to measure the vertical displacement of the two points on the boundary between white and black regions, the specimen is correctly divided into halves through the thickness direction and one of them is painted by white correction fluid. After the effects of the position of gauge points and their length on measuring the transverse strain are checked [2], the gauge length is decided to 5mm and one gauge point (No.1) is apart 1mm and the another (No.2) is 6mm from the left support. Namely, the vertical displacement of the points crossing the gauge line and the black/white boundary line is measured.

Fig. 2 shows the experimental apparatuses for the static loading and the gauge length adaptor is attached to two lenses of the electro optical extensometer and this extensometer faces the direction of beam axis. The static load is measured by a load cell and the average transverse shear stress and the transverse shear strength are obtained by the following equations.

Fig.2 Experimental apparatuses for static loading

$$\tau_{ts} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{P}{bh}, \quad F_{ts} = \frac{3}{4} \frac{P_{max}}{bh} \quad (1)$$

in which, P is the load in the elastic limit, P_{max} is the maximum load at failure, b and h are the width and thickness of specimen. w_1 and w_2 are the vertical displacement of No.1 and No.2 measured by the electro optical extensometer and they include w_{b1} and w_{b2} which are displacements by flexural deformation. Then the transverse shear strain is calculated by the following equations.

$$\gamma_{ts} = \frac{(w_2 - w_{2b}) - (w_1 - w_{1b})}{x_2 - x_1} \quad (2)$$

$$w_{1b} = \frac{Px_1}{12EI} \left(\frac{3}{4}L^2 - x_1^2 \right), \quad w_{2b} = \frac{Px_2}{12EI} \left(\frac{3}{4}L^2 - x_2^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

where, L is the distance ($=15\text{mm}$) between two supports, x_1 and x_2 are the distance ($=1$ and 6mm) from the left support and EI is the flexural rigidity of the specimen. After amplifying the experimental data, converting from analogue data to digital ones and inputting them to a personal computer, the average transverse shear stress, shear strain and shear strength are calculated by the equations mentioned above. Then the transverse shear moduli are obtained by the initial slope of $\tau_{ts} - \gamma_{ts}$ figures.

In the case of impact loading, a drop weight equipment is used instead of a static load equipment. Mass of the drop weight is 200g and it freely falls to the specimen. The impact load is measured by using load cells set inside of the supports. Except for measuring a velocity just before impact, other measurement is same as one in the static loading (Fig.3).

Fig.3 Experimental apparatuses for impact loading

ANALYTICAL EQUATION AND 3D FEM

Let 1 and 2 axes are fibers and their normal directions of the unidirectional laminate and x, y are the axial and width directions of the beam specimen. When x axis is rotated from 1 axis and its angle of the clockwise direction is θ , the transverse shear modulus in this case is given as follows [3]

$$G_{zx} = \frac{G_{23} \cdot G_{31}}{G_{31} \sin^2 \theta + G_{23} \cos^2 \theta} \quad (4)$$

where, G_{31} and G_{23} are the transverse shear modulus of 0° and 90° specimens. In the case of the symmetric laminates, its transverse shear modulus is obtained by the following equations.

$$G_{zx} = \frac{A_{44} \cdot A_{55} - A_{45}^2}{A_{44} \cdot h} \quad (5)$$

$$A_{ij} = \frac{5}{4} \sum_{k=1}^N (\overline{Q}_{ij})_k \left[h_k - h_{k-1} - \frac{4}{3} (h_k^3 - h_{k-1}^3) \frac{1}{h^2} \right] \quad (6)$$

(i, j = 4, 5)

where \overline{Q}_{ij} is the transformed reduced stiffness and N is the number of lamination.

In order to examine the stress distribution and the deformation at failure by cross elasticity effect, PAFEC which is one of a three dimensional FEM code is used here. The total elements obtained by the divisions of 22 elements, 10 elements and 24 elements in the axial, width and thickness directions are 5280. The static load is assumed to distribute over a region of 1.0mm around the load point. The displacements of the load point are prevented in the axial and width directions and all displacements of the supports are also prevented. The mechanical properties used in the FEM analysis are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of CFRP

Properties	Unit	TR330E-150S
E _x	GPa	133
E _y	GPa	8.93
E _z	GPa	8.93
G _{xy}	GPa	4.61
G _{zx}	GPa	3.95
G _{yz}	GPa	0.522
ν _{xy}	-	0.30
ν _{yx}	-	0.02
ν _{yz}	-	0.37
ν _{zy}	-	0.37
ν _{xz}	-	0.30
ν _{zx}	-	0.02

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig.4 shows the relations of the static load and the transverse shear strain from the beginning to the failure load for $[0^\circ]_{24}$, $[30^\circ]_{24}$, $[45^\circ]_{24}$, $[60^\circ]_{24}$ and $[90^\circ]_{24}$ specimens. There are nonlinear curves in all cases and even the curve of $[0^\circ]_{24}$ is remarkable. The initial slope of curves in Fig. 4 decreases as of the fiber orientation angle θ increasing. The load at failure is the largest in the specimen of $[0^\circ]_{24}$ and the transverse shear strain at failure is the largest in the specimen of $[30^\circ]_{24}$.

Fig.4 Static load VS. Transverse shear strain

Fig. 5 also shows the relations of the impact load and the transverse shear strain from the beginning to the failure load.

Although the high frequency modes appear in the nonlinear relations, the initial slope decreases as θ increasing and the impact failure load is the largest in the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ as same as the static load. However the impact transverse shear failure strain is the largest in the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ and decreases as θ increasing.

Fig. 6 shows the changes of the static and impact transverse shear moduli to the fiber orientation

angle θ . Both experimental moduli decrease as θ increasing and fairly agree with ones calculated by equation (3). Consequently, the static and impact transverse shear moduli of the unidirectional laminate having any fiber orientation angle can be obtained by the values of the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ and $[90^\circ]_{24}$ laminates. The impact transverse shear modulus is about 0.5GPa larger than the static one.

Table 2 shows that the experimental transverse shear moduli of the cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates accord with ones calculated by equation (4) and that the transverse shear modulus of the symmetric laminates having any stacking sequence can be obtained using by the classical lamination theory.

The relations of the static and impact transverse shear strength to the fiber orientation angle θ are shown in Fig. 7. The impact value is larger than the static one at θ less than 30° and they become almost same value after 30° . Both curves have the point of inflection near 30° and the transverse shear failure in the specimens of $[0^\circ]_{24}$ and $[15^\circ]_{24}$ is confirmed using by the flaw detection with ultrasonic technique. Otherwise, the flexural failure is observed between $[40^\circ]_{24}$ and $[90^\circ]_{24}$ specimens and these combined failure modes appear in the specimen having the fiber orientation angle of near 30° .

The relations of the static and impact transverse shear failure strain to the fiber orientation angle θ are shown in Fig.8. The static value reaches the maximum at 30° and decreases as θ increasing. The

Fig.5 Impact load VS. Transverse shear strain

Fig.6 Variations of transverse shear moduli with fiber orientation angle

Table 2 Comparisons of transverse shear moduli for symmetric laminate

		cross-ply	quasi-isotropic
Calculation	G _{zx} (GPa)	2.71	2.66
Experiment	G _{zx} (GPa)	2.89	2.84
	CV (%)	9.85	16.2

impact one has the maximum at 0° and also decreases as θ increasing. Since the flexural failure appears in the specimen having the fiber orientation angle of over 30° , the failure strain of specimens over 30° is not the transverse shear failure strain in the strict sense of the word. Therefore, the fiber orientation angle of the unidirectional laminate is restricted to less than 30° when the short beam method is used in order to get the transverse shear failure strain.

Fig. 9 shows the distribution of τ_{15} in the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ specimen obtained by the 3D FEM. Although the stress concentrations appear near the support and the load point, this distribution is almost in accord with one obtained by the flaw detection with ultrasonic technique as shown in Fig.10. Figs.11 show the deformation of $[0^\circ]_{24}$, $[15^\circ]_{24}$, $[30^\circ]_{24}$ and $[45^\circ]_{24}$ specimens, respectively. In the case of $[0^\circ]_{24}$ and $[15^\circ]_{24}$ specimens, the shear deformation mainly appears in the central plane through the thickness direction, but the flexural deformation begins to appear with the increase of the fiber orientation angle. In the case of $[45^\circ]_{24}$ specimen, torsional deformation with the flexural deformation also appears owing to cross elasticity effect.

Fig.7 Variations of transverse shear strength with fiber orientation angle

Fig.8 Variations of transverse shear failure strain with fiber orientation angle

Fig.9 Distribution of transverse shear stress in the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ obtained by FEM

As a result, the unidirectional laminate having the fiber orientation angle of over 30° is subject to these flexural and torsional deformations and these specimens are not only broken by the pure transverse shear mentioned above.

Fig.10 Distribution of transverse shear stress in the $[0^\circ]_{24}$ obtained by flaw detection with ultrasonic technique

Figs.11 Deformations of $[0^\circ]_{24}$, $[15^\circ]_{24}$, $[30^\circ]_{24}$ and $[45^\circ]_{24}$ obtained by FEM

CONCLUSIONS

- (1) This paper shows the first experiment for obtaining the static and impact transverse shear moduli, both failure strains and both nonlinear relations of transverse shear stress and strain using by the newly devised electro optical extensometer.
- (2) Both experimental moduli under the static and impact loading agree with the analytical ones. Consequently, the static and impact transverse shear moduli of the unidirectional laminates having any fiber orientation angle can be obtained by the values of the 0° and 90° laminates.
- (3) The impact transverse shear modulus is about 0.5GPa larger than the static one for all fiber orientation angles.
- (4) The experimental transverse shear moduli of the cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates accord with the analytical ones and the transverse shear modulus of symmetric laminates having any stacking sequence can be obtained using by classical lamination theory.
- (5) The unidirectional laminate having the fiber orientation angle of over 30° is subject to the flexural and torsional deformations and these specimens are not only broken by the pure transverse shear. Therefore, the fiber orientation angle of the unidirectional laminate is restricted to less than 30° when the short beam method is used in order to get the transverse shear failure strain.

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